

1 **Strontium doping and impregnation onto alumina improve the NO_x**
2 **storage and reduction capacity of LaCoO₃ perovskites**

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Highlights

- Strontium doping enhances NO_x storage and reduction performance of bulk LaCoO₃.
- 30% is the optimum strontium doping degree for bulk perovskites, La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃.
- A more efficient use of the perovskite can be achieved by supporting it over Al₂O₃.
- Perovskite loading around 30% over Al₂O₃ maximizes its utilization.
- NSR performance was better for Al₂O₃ supported perovskites than bulk ones.

30 **ABSTRACT**

31 Here we report the effects of strontium doping of perovskites ($\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$) on NO_x
32 storage and reduction (NSR) as well as the effects of supporting the perovskite onto an
33 alumina support. The NSR capacity of $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ improved with strontium doping:
34 this material displayed a good balance between NO oxidation capacity and adsorption
35 sites accessibility. Increased accessibility was mainly due to the strontium oxide
36 segregates. In addition, different loadings of $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ perovskite (10, 20, 30, 40
37 and 50%) were impregnated onto alumina in order to increase the exposed surface area
38 of the perovskite. This had the effect of increasing the NSR capacity of the perovskite.
39 The results of X-Ray diffraction, UV–vis–NIR spectroscopy, N_2 adsorption-desorption,
40 electron microscopy, and temperature programmed techniques, demonstrated that the
41 cobalt ions preferably formed cobalt aluminate (CoAl_2O_4) in the case of low perovskite
42 loadings (<20%). Meanwhile, a well-developed perovskite phase was observed with the
43 higher loadings (>30%). The specific NO oxidation rate per gram of perovskite
44 increased dramatically with the incorporation onto an alumina support. 30%
45 LSCO/ Al_2O_3 sample had an oxidation rate of $138 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} (\text{g LSCO})^{-1}$ at $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$,
46 more than double the rate of the bulk $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ ($49 \mu\text{mol min}^{-1} (\text{g LSCO})^{-1}$).
47 Likewise, the 30% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 sample had a higher NO_x storage capacity than its bulk
48 counterpart at $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$: 306 vs. $115 \mu\text{mol} (\text{g LSCO})^{-1}$. The higher oxidation capacity of
49 the alumina-supported samples also facilitated the diffusion of the intermediate
50 compounds from oxidation to adsorption sites. Impregnating alumina with perovskite
51 could be used to improve the efficiency of perovskite mediated NO_x removal in
52 automobile applications. Furthermore, adding palladium onto optimum alumina-
53 supported perovskite sample, i.e. 1.5% Pd-30% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 , resulted in a clear
54 improvement in NO_x storage and reduction capacity. This last sample demonstrated a
55 nitrogen yield as high as 65%, an improvement over the model Pt-based NSR catalyst.

56

57 1. INTRODUCTION

58 Diesel engines operate under conditions of high air to fuel ratios. These high ratios lead
59 to better fuel efficiency and lower CO₂ emissions than stoichiometric gasoline engines.
60 However, the net oxidizing environment in the exhaust makes three-way catalysts
61 (TWCs) inefficient for use in NO_x reduction applications [1]. Consequently, alternative
62 catalytic strategies for reducing NO_x emissions need to be developed. NO_x storage and
63 reduction (NSR) [2] and selective catalytic reduction (SCR) [3] methods are the most
64 promising avenues for exploration. NSR technology works under cycled fuel-lean and
65 fuel-rich feedstreams using Pt-BaO/Al₂O₃ as the model composition for the catalyst.
66 During the lean period, NO is oxidized into NO₂ over the platinum. Nitrites or nitrates
67 [4, 5] then form over an alkali or an alkali-earth material, such as barium. This process
68 facilitates NO_x storage. The environment periodically switches to rich conditions via
69 injection of a reductant such as H₂, CO or HC. As a consequence, the stored nitrates are
70 released and reduced over the platinum sites.

71 One of the main drawbacks of the NSR technology is the high cost of noble metals,
72 especially Pt. Another is the poor thermal stability of these metals under highly
73 oxidative conditions [6]. Perovskites have recently gained attention for use in oxidation
74 processes as a low-cost alternative to noble metals [7]. The perovskite lattice can be
75 described using the general formula ABO₃, where the B cation coordinates with oxygen
76 in the octahedral structure, and A cation is found in the centre of a dodecahedral
77 structure. Perovskites are excellent catalysts of oxidation reactions. The catalytic
78 activity of perovskites is modulated by the concentration of oxygen vacancies, the type
79 of B cation, and the redox ability of the B cation [8].

80 We recently reported that the partial substitution of lanthanum by strontium in LaCoO₃
81 and LaMnO₃ perovskites improved NO-to-NO₂ oxidation activity beyond that of the
82 model Pt-based catalyst formulation [9]. In this study, strontium doped perovskites (La_{1-x}
83 Sr_xCoO₃) were exhaustively characterized in terms of specific surface area, oxygen
84 vacancies and surface Sr concentration. Of the materials assessed, La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃
85 catalyst had the highest NO oxidation capacity. In NSR technology, NO oxidation
86 capacity is the most important parameter for improving the storage of NO_x [10]. The
87 NO_x storage and reduction capacities of bulk perovskites were not analysed in this
88 study.

89 Meanwhile, other studies have demonstrated that strontium substitutions of lanthanum
90 could modulate the NO_x-to-N₂ efficiency of perovskite-based catalysts [11, 12].
91 Therefore, the first objective of the study presented here was to determine the Sr-doping
92 level that was optimum for NO_x removal. In order to accomplish this objective, we set
93 out to uncover the relationship between the physico-chemical properties of La_{1-x}
94 _xSr_xCoO₃ perovskites and the capacity to store, release, and reduce NO_x.

95 The low exposed surface area (around 20 m² g⁻¹) of perovskite is a consequence of
96 agglomeration during the calcination step and is one of the primary limitations of the
97 bulk La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO₃ formulations. Two approaches could be used to overcome this
98 limitation: synthesizing mesostructured perovskites via nanocasting, and/or the
99 distribution of the perovskite over high surface area supports [13, 14]. Mesoporous
100 supports have been tried in the past. For example, overlaying ZrTiO₄ with LaCoO₃
101 perovskite had already been found to reduce the tendency of perovskite to sinter and to
102 improve NO_x storage capacity [15]. More recently, You et al. [16, 17] found that ceria-
103 supported and Ce_{0.75}Zr_{0.25}O₂-supported LaCoO₃ perovskite had a high NSR capacity
104 despite having a low specific surface area (below 50 m² g⁻¹).

105 γ -Al₂O₃ is another mesoporous support with high specific surface area and physico-
106 chemical properties that are suitable for use in NSR applications [18]. However, to our
107 knowledge, the feasibility of using alumina-supported perovskites for the storage and
108 reduction of NO_x in automobile applications has not yet been studied. Therefore, the
109 second objective of this study was to determine the efficacy of depositing perovskites
110 over an alumina mesoporous support in order to increase thermal stability. In the
111 present work, a series of alumina-supported perovskites were prepared by wetness
112 impregnation. The prepared samples were characterized and tested for NO oxidation
113 activity (NO-to-NO₂ conversion) and NO_x storage and reduction (NO_x-to-N₂ efficiency)
114 capacities. In this way, NSR catalytic behaviour was linked to the physico-chemical
115 properties of the samples. The properties and performance of the alumina-supported
116 samples were then compared with the unsupported bulk perovskite formulations.

117 **2. EXPERIMENTAL**

118 **2.1. Perovskite-based catalyst preparation.** Perovskites were synthesized by the
119 citric acid sol-gel method [19]. Bulk La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO₃ catalysts were prepared using the

120 optimal synthesis conditions already reported by our group [9]. Appropriate amounts of
121 $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (*Fluka*, 99%), $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (*Sigma Aldrich*, 98%) and $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$
122 (*Sigma Aldrich*, 99%) were added to obtain perovskites with different degrees strontium
123 doping. All salts were dissolved by vigorous stirring in distilled water. Citric acid
124 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, *Sigma Aldrich*, 99%) was then added as a complexing agent at a citrate
125 to nitrate molar ratio of 1.1. The pH was adjusted to a value of 8 with an ammonia
126 solution (25% as NH_3 , *Panreac*). After solvent evaporation at 80 °C, the gel was further
127 dried at 120 °C overnight. The material was then calcined at 650 °C for 4h under a flow
128 of 5% O_2/He in order to achieve the perovskite structure. The following samples were
129 synthesized (listed from low to high Sr substitutions of La): LaCoO_3 , $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{CoO}_3$,
130 $\text{La}_{0.8}\text{Sr}_{0.2}\text{CoO}_3$, $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$, $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{CoO}_3$ and $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{CoO}_3$.

131 Alumina-supported perovskites were prepared by wetness impregnation. Nominal
132 perovskite loadings of 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 wt% were used. Initially, γ -alumina
133 (SA6173, Saint-Gobain) was pre-calcined at 700 °C for 4 h in static air. The perovskite
134 precursors were then dissolved together with citric acid up to a concentration of 0.95
135 mol L^{-1} . This mixture was added to the alumina inside a rotary evaporator (under
136 vacuum at 35 °C) in order to obtain a homogeneously distributed gel precursor over the
137 alumina [20]. Finally, the supported gel was calcined in 5% O_2/He following the same
138 calcination protocol used for bulk perovskite samples.

139 Pd-impregnated samples were prepared by sequential incorporation of the same
140 palladium load (1.5 wt%) over optimum alumina-supported perovskite or bulk
141 perovskite using wetness impregnation. Tretaamminepalladium (II) nitrate solution was
142 used as the precursor [$\text{Pd}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_3)_2$]. The resulting samples were calcined at 500 °C
143 for 4 h in static air. The following samples were synthesized: Pd-LSCO/ Al_2O_3 and
144 Pd/LSCO.

145 **2.2. Preparation of the LNT model catalyst.** This sample was prepared by
146 consecutive wetness impregnation of Pt and Ba over alumina. First, a specific load of
147 platinum was incorporated into the alumina support by dissolving the adequate amount
148 of tretaammineplatinum (II) nitrate [$\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_3)_2$] into distilled water. The process
149 was repeated for barium incorporation using the adequate amount of barium acetate

150 [Ba(CH₃COO)₂] as precursor. The nominal loadings for Pt and BaO were 1.5% and
151 15%, respectively. After each impregnation, the catalyst was calcined at 500 °C for 4 h.

152 **2.3. Catalysts characterization.** XRD diffractions patterns of the samples were
153 obtained using a Philips PW1710 diffractometer. The samples were finely ground and
154 subjected to Cu K_α radiation in a continuous scan mode from 5° to 70° 2θ with a 0.02°
155 per second sampling interval. Data treatment was carried out using the PANalytical
156 X^{pert} HighScore software. The Scherrer equation was used to calculate the crystallite
157 size of the La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO₃ perovskites using the 2θ = 33.3° diffraction line broadening.

158 La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ perovskite loading was determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma
159 Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-AES). The analysis was carried out using a mass
160 spectrometer containing plasma source (Q-ICP-MS XSeries II model of Thermo). Prior
161 to the analysis, the samples were digested at 120 °C with a mixture HNO₃:HCl=1:3.

162 The textural properties of the samples were determined by N₂ adsorption-desorption at
163 77 K, using a Micromeritics TriStar equipment.

164 The reducibility of the samples was investigated using the Micromeritics AutoChem II
165 system. The quartz tube reactor was loaded with 0.1 g of sample and pretreated in 30
166 mL min⁻¹ of 5% O₂/He mixture at 600 °C for 30 min followed by a cooling step down to
167 50 °C. The samples were then heated from room temperature to 950 °C under a 10 °C
168 min⁻¹ temperature ramp in a 30 mL min⁻¹ gas flow of 5% H₂/Ar. Water generated during
169 the reduction was trapped using a cold trap. The gas stream was then analyzed by the
170 TCD detector.

171 In order to determine the distribution of the perovskite, transmission electron
172 microscopy (TEM) images were taken using a JEOL (JEM-2010) microscope. Prior to
173 the analysis, some drops of an ultrasonically dispersed suspension of each sample in
174 ethanol were placed on a copper grid with lacey carbon film and dried under ambient
175 conditions.

176 UV-Vis Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-vis-DRS) was used to characterize the
177 cobalt species found in the bulk and alumina-supported samples. The analyses were
178 carried out at room temperature with a UV-vis-NIR Cary 5000 apparatus coupled to a
179 Diffuse Reflectance Internal 2500. The range of wavelengths used was 200–2500 nm.

180 **2.4 Catalytic activity.** The catalytic tests were carried out using a total flow rate of
181 2000 mL min⁻¹ and a catalyst particle size of 0.3-0.5 mm. These experimental
182 conditions guaranteed the absence of external and internal mass transfer limitations [9].

183 *2.4.1. NO-to-NO₂ oxidation activity.* NO oxidation tests were carried out in a vertical
184 stainless steel reactor filled with 0.5 grams of catalyst. The reactor was located inside a
185 3-zone tube furnace. The feedstream composition was: 500 ppm NO, 6% O₂, and Ar as
186 the balance gas. The flow rate was 2000 mL min⁻¹. Stable NO and NO₂ signals were
187 observed once the steady state was reached at each temperature (approximately 20
188 minutes after the temperature was stabilized). These signals were plugged into Equation
189 (1) in order calculate the NO-to-NO₂ conversion values.

$$190 \quad X_{\text{NO-to-NO}_2} (\%) = \frac{F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{out}}}{F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

191 where $F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}}$ is the NO molar flow ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$) at the inlet, $F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{out}}$ is the NO molar flow
192 ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$) at the outlet.

193 The average specific reaction rates of NO oxidation per mass unit of the perovskite
194 (W_{LSCO}) at 350 °C was calculated by Equation 2:

$$195 \quad \bar{R}_{\text{NO}} [\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{min}^{-1} \cdot (\text{g LSCO})^{-1}] = \frac{F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}} - F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{out}}}{W_{\text{LSCO}}} = \frac{F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}} \cdot X_{\text{NO-to-NO}_2}}{W_{\text{LSCO}}} \quad (2)$$

196 *2.4.2. NO_x storage and reduction (NSR) experiments.* NSR tests were carried out in the
197 same reactor. During the lean period (150 s), the feed composition was 500 ppm NO,
198 6% O₂, and Ar as the balance gas. During the rich period (20 s), oxygen was replaced by
199 hydrogen at a concentration of 3%. Gases were fed via mass flow controllers. The flow
200 rate was set to 2000 mL min⁻¹ during both periods. Thus, the weight hourly space
201 velocity (WHSV) was 5000 $\mu\text{mol h}^{-1} (\text{g cat.})^{-1}$ during all experiments. Temperature was
202 continuously monitored via a thermocouple found inside the catalytic bed.

203 The outlet gas composition was continuously measured using a MKS MultiGas 2030
204 FT-IR analyzer linked to a MKS Cirrus quadrupole MS. NO, NO₂, NH₃, N₂O, and H₂O
205 were quantitatively monitored by the FT-IR analyzer, whereas H₂, N₂, and O₂ were
206 qualitatively monitored by the MS analyzer. The activity of the catalyst during the lean
207 and rich periods was evaluated in terms of the parameters [21, 22] listed below.

208 NO_x storage capacity (NSC): percentage of NO_x stored during the lean period as a
 209 function of the amount of NO found at the inlet, as described by Equation 3.

$$210 \quad NSC (\%) = \frac{F_{NO}^{in} t_L - \int_0^{t_L} F_{NOx}^{out} dt}{F_{NO}^{in}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

211 where F_{NOx}^{out} is the NO_x molar flow ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$) at the outlet and t_L (min) is the length of
 212 the lean cycle.

213 The NO_x storage capacity at 400°C was also normalized against the unit of perovskite
 214 mass (W_{LSCO}), as follows:

$$215 \quad NSC [\mu\text{mol} \cdot (\text{g LSCO})^{-1}] = \frac{F_{NO}^{in} t_L - \int_0^{t_L} F_{NOx}^{out} dt}{W_{LSCO}} \quad (4)$$

216 The above equation can be directly applied to bulk perovskite samples. However, due to
 217 the NO_x storage capacity of the alumina, Equation 4 had to be modified in order to
 218 avoid overestimating the specific NO_x storage capacity of the perovskite in the alumina-
 219 supported samples. In the case of the alumina containing samples, the NSC of the bare
 220 alumina had to be subtracted from the numerator of Equation 4, while taking into
 221 account the specific weight of alumina in each sample.

222 NO_x global conversion (X_{NOx}): percentage of NO_x converted during the whole operation
 223 (lean and rich cycles) with respect to the total amount of NO fed into the reactor
 224 (Equation 5),

$$225 \quad X_{NOx} (\%) = \frac{F_{NO}^{in} (t_L + t_R) - \int_0^{t_L+t_R} F_{NOx}^{out} dt}{F_{NO}^{in} (t_L + t_R)} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

226 where t_R (min) is the length of the rich cycle.

227 Yield of N -compounds ($Y_{NH_3}, Y_{N_2O}, Y_{N_2}$): defined as the mole percent of the
 228 corresponding component at the outlet in relation to NO amount at the inlet, i.e.:

$$229 \quad Y_{NH_3} (\%) = \frac{\int_0^{t_L+t_R} F_{NH_3}^{out} dt}{F_{NO}^{in} (t_L + t_R)} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

$$Y_{\text{N}_2\text{O}} (\%) = \frac{\int_0^{t_L+t_R} 2F_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}^{\text{out}} dt}{F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}} (t_L + t_R)} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

$$Y_{\text{N}_2} (\%) = \frac{\int_0^{t_L+t_R} 2F_{\text{N}_2}^{\text{out}} dt}{F_{\text{NO}}^{\text{in}} (t_L + t_R)} \times 100 \quad (8)$$

where $F_{\text{NH}_3}^{\text{out}}$, $F_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}^{\text{out}}$ and $F_{\text{N}_2}^{\text{out}}$ are the molar flow ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$) of NH_3 , N_2O , and N_2 at the outlet.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. NO_x storage and reduction behavior of strontium doped LaCoO_3 . Figure 1 shows how the outlet concentrations of NO , NO_2 , NO_x , NH_3 , and N_2O evolved during two consecutive lean and rich cycles. The measurements were taken at 400°C once steady state had been achieved. Both bare LaCoO_3 perovskite (Figure 1a) and the strontium doped $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ sample (Figure 1b) were assessed. The latter sample has the highest reported NO oxidation capacity among strontium doped perovskites samples [9]. The lowest NO , NO_2 and NO_x outlet concentrations were observed during the beginning of the lean cycle. This is due to NO_x adsorption on the perovskite. NO_x adsorption occurs via two mechanisms: 1) NO_2 is adsorbed by the basic storage components, either strontium or lanthanum terminated perovskite surfaces or highly dispersed segregated SrO and La_2O_3 [23], after which a disproportionation reaction generates nitrate and facilitates the release of NO [24, 25], and ii) NO_2 is adsorbed via oxygen vacancies on the surface of the perovskite.

As the lean period progresses, the NO_x storage sites became progressively saturated. In the case of the LaCoO_3 perovskite, the NO_x outlet concentration increases gradually until it matches the inlet concentration of 500 ppm NO . At this point, the catalyst is saturated with NO_x . Only NO was introduced in the feedstream. The outlet concentration of NO_2 is nearly as high as outlet concentration of NO . These observations demonstrate the high oxidation activity of the perovskites. In the subsequent rich period, oxygen is replaced with hydrogen. The hydrogen reacts with the stored NO_x , generating NH_3 , N_2O , and N_2 . The maximum outlet concentration of ammonia was 250 and 350 ppm, for LaCoO_3 and $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$, respectively. However, the N_2O concentration did not differ and was maintained at around 50 ppm.

258 In addition, some of the stored NO_x was released without being converted. In the case of
259 LaCoO₃ perovskite, the peak corresponding to the released NO peak reaches 1200 ppm.
260 In the case of the La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ variant, the NO peak reaches 3000 ppm.

261 The catalytic performance of La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO₃ perovskites was compared at 400 °C by
262 calculating the NO_x storage capacity (*NSC*, Equation 3) using data from NO_x storage
263 and reduction experiments (Figure S1). Quantitative data are shown in Table 1. Higher
264 strontium doping generally has a beneficial effect on the NO_x adsorption capacity of the
265 samples. The adsorption capacity is proportional to the shaded areas of Figure S1. The
266 *NSC* of the LaCoO₃ perovskite was 33.6% since 34.8 μmol (g LSCO)⁻¹ of the NO feed
267 was stored (Table 1). The *NSC* of La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ variant was 55.8% since 57.8 μmol
268 (g LSCO)⁻¹ of the NO feed was stored, a much better outcome (Table 1). The better NO_x
269 storage capacity of the La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ variant is probably due to a higher NO-to-NO₂
270 oxidation conversion rate, an increase in oxygen vacancy accessibility, and a higher
271 exposed surface area.

272 The charge imbalance produced by strontium (Sr²⁺) substitution of lanthanum (La³⁺) is
273 balanced by the formation of oxygen vacancies [9]. Strontium doping also results in the
274 surface enrichment of strontium or even in the formation of a segregated bulk strontium
275 phase. These could function as NO_x trapping sites. Nevertheless, strontium doping at
276 proportions higher than 30% did not further enhance the *NSC*. Indeed, the *NSC* went
277 down to 56.1 and 52.6 μmol (g LSCO)⁻¹ with the La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}CoO₃ and La_{0.5}Sr_{0.5}CoO₃
278 samples, respectively. This slight decrease in the *NSC* could be due to the lower specific
279 surface area of samples doped with higher strontium loadings [9]. Thus, 30% is the
280 optimal level of strontium doping for enhancing the NO_x storage capacity of this class
281 of perovskites.

282 NO_x conversion values (*X*_{NO_x}, Equation 5) were analyzed in order to determine and
283 compare NO_x storage and reduction capacities. *X*_{NO_x} is defined as the amount of NO_x
284 converted with respect to the total amount of NO fed into the reactor during the entire
285 lean-rich cycle. Improving the capacity for NO_x storage is a key step towards obtaining
286 favorable global NO_x conversion outcomes. Thus we hypothesized that strontium
287 doping should improve *X*_{NO_x} values just as doping had improved *NSC* values. In fact,
288 this is what was observed (Table 1). However, in order to obtain high global NO_x
289 conversion values, effective reduction of the stored NO_x during the rich period had to

290 also be achieved. Among the perovskites studied, the $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ variant gave the
291 highest global NO_x conversion value (14.5%). This value corresponded to $17.0 \mu\text{mol}$
292 $(\text{g LSCO})^{-1}$, a quantity much lower than the NO_x storage capacity of the sample (57.8
293 $\mu\text{mol} (\text{g LSCO})^{-1}$). A remarkable fraction of NO_x stored during the lean period was
294 released to the gas phase during the rich period but was not converted (Figure 1).

295 Also important for NO_x removal in automobile applications is that nitrogen formation
296 should be selected for and that byproduct formation should be disfavored. The nitrogen
297 production values (Y_{N_2} , Equation 8) are shown in Table 1. There is a good correlation
298 between NSC , X_{NO_x} and Y_{N_2} values. The $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ variant had the highest nitrogen
299 production value. Nevertheless, the Y_{N_2} was very low: 6.9%. This corresponded to 4.0
300 $\mu\text{mol N}_2 (\text{g LSCO})^{-1}$ formation. Meanwhile, $17.0 \mu\text{mol} (\text{g LSCO})^{-1}$ of byproducts were
301 generated. These byproducts included such as NH_3 and N_2O .

302 **FIGURE 1**

303 **TABLE 1**

304 Reaction temperatures also affected NSC , X_{NO_x} , and Y_{N_2} values (Figure 2). The results
305 of NO_x storage and reduction experiments for $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ perovskite at different
306 temperatures can be observed in Figure S2. Generally speaking, NSC (Figure 2a) is
307 enhanced by strontium doping (as already discussed) and reaction temperature. Two
308 patterns emerge with respect to the effects temperature had on the reaction process. In
309 the case of weak strontium doping of samples, such as in the case of LaCoO_3 and
310 $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{CoO}_3$, the NSC value increased almost linearly with temperature. In the case of
311 more extensive doping, such as in $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$, $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{CoO}_3$ and $\text{La}_{0.5}\text{Sr}_{0.5}\text{CoO}_3$,
312 the NSC increased exponentially until a shoulder was reached at $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Basic NO_x
313 storage components such as BaO , K_2O , SrO or CaO that are deposited onto an oxide
314 support have a volcano-type dependence on the temperature. Typically, maximum NSC
315 values for these compounds are observed at around $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [2, 21, 25-27]. Thus, there
316 was a notable increase of NSC at around $350 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the case of high strontium doping of
317 samples. This improvement in NSC is a consequence of a segregated or bulk strontium
318 oxide phase (SrO), whose presence in these samples has been confirmed [9].

319 At temperatures above 350 °C, the NO_x adsorption capacity of bulk storage components
320 was lower. This is due to the decreased stability of the NO_x species being adsorbed [2,
321 22, 26-28]. In contrast, high strontium loads are associated with higher *NSC* values for
322 temperatures above 350 °C, with a maximum *NSC* at 450 °C.

323 There appear to be many different NO_x adsorption sites in the perovskite material.
324 Firstly, NO_x can be adsorbed on the bulk strontium oxide phase, which enhances the
325 *NSC* at around 350 °C. Secondly, NO_x can be adsorbed on the active storage sites found
326 on the surface of the perovskite. These sites become more efficient at higher
327 temperatures. These surface active sites are found in the LaCoO₃ and La_{0.9}Sr_{0.1}CoO₃
328 variants, which lack a bulk strontium oxide phase [9]. Those samples which were highly
329 substituted with strontium demonstrated an exceptionally high *NSC* at high
330 temperatures (as high as 65% at 450 °C). This result is in agreement with previous
331 research [24, 29]. Strontium appears to the surface of the material [11], a process which
332 provides additional NO_x storage sites. Above 450 °C, a reduction in *NSC* values was
333 observed for all samples (data shown for La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ only). Adsorbed NO_x species
334 were unstable at this temperature range. This limited the storage capacity of this
335 material.

336 Figure 2b is a plot of global NO_x conversion versus temperature. A low X_{NO_x} was
337 calculated for all samples when the system was kept at temperatures below 250 °C. Low
338 X_{NO_x} values are associated with low *NSC* values (<20%).

339 Meanwhile, for the highly doped samples, a prominent increase in the X_{NO_x} was
340 observed at 300 °C, specifically for high strontium doped samples. This result is
341 consistent with the increase in *NSC*. At temperatures above 350 °C, *NSC* values
342 increased further (Figure 2a), while the X_{NO_x} values remained constant or went down.

343 The bulk strontium oxide functions as the primary NO_x trapping site at around 350 °C.
344 The bulk strontium oxide also supplies highly stable trapping sites that slow down the
345 decomposition rate of the NO_x adsorbed during the rich period. In this way, the
346 hydrogen reduction of NO_x is promoted [11].

347 At temperatures above 350 °C, the NO_x trapping efficiency of bulk strontium oxide
348 decreases [10]. At this point, the perovskite NO_x trapping sites functions as the main
349 trapping site. It appears that, during the rich period, the rate of NO_x decomposition in

350 sites found in the perovskite exceed the rate in sites found in the bulk strontium oxide.
351 This is consistent with data that show that, at higher temperatures, more NO_x is released
352 without being converted (Figure S2). Therefore, at temperatures above 350 °C, an
353 increase in the *NSC* does not result in a parallel increase in global NO_x conversion. This
354 is because NO_x reduction is a rate limiting step in the conversion process.

355 Similarly, nitrogen production peaked at 10% at 300-350 °C (Figure 2c). For some
356 samples, nitrogen production decreased at temperatures above 350 °C. This is due to the
357 formation of ammonia instead of nitrogen (Figure S3), which in turn limits the
358 generation of N₂O.

359 **FIGURE 2**

360 Substituting La for Sr not only promotes the conversion of NO to NO₂, but also
361 improves NO_x storage and reduction capacity, in particular the NO_x storage capacity
362 (*NSC*). This effect is due to the segregated bulk strontium oxide.

363 However, the NO_x storage capacity should be further enhanced, so that the material
364 works well at the lower temperatures required for commercial applications. The main
365 limitations of perovskites are the insufficient number of storage sites [16, 17] and the
366 limited specific surface area [30, 31].

367 With the aim of increasing the specific surface area and improving storage site
368 accessibility, we assessed the effects of incorporating the perovskite onto a alumina
369 support. To that end, we selected La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ as the model sample for incorporation
370 onto the alumina. Of the strontium doped perovskites tested, this variant has the best
371 NO-to-NO₂ conversion value [9], NO_x storage capacity, global NO_x conversion value,
372 and nitrogen production value.

373 **3.2. Alumina-supported perovskites for NO_x storage and reduction.** LSCO/Al₂O₃
374 samples were prepared by wetness impregnation of La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ (LSCO) using
375 nominal perovskite loadings of 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 wt%.

376 *3.2.1. Characterization of LSCO/Al₂O₃ samples.* Figure 3 shows the XRD patterns of the
377 alumina-supported samples as well as reference unsupported perovskite (LSCO) and
378 alumina. Intense diffraction peaks, which are marked with hollow circles (○), can be
379 observed for the bulk LSCO perovskite. These peaks are characteristic of highly

380 crystalline structures. The wide peaks observed at 37.6, 45.9 and 67.0 ° are identified
381 with solid triangles (▲) and indicate a highly disordered cubic alumina structure with
382 low crystallinity.

383

FIGURE 3

384 XRD analysis of supported perovskites resulted in diffraction peaks of varying
385 intensity. Some of these peaks were characteristic of alumina, while others were
386 characteristic of bulk perovskite. Additional phases were not detected. As expected, a
387 lower level of perovskite loading reduced the perovskite signal.

388 The crystal size of the perovskite phase of each sample was assessed in order to
389 determine the crystallinity (Table 2). The 50% LSCO/Al₂O₃ crystals were equal
390 diameter to bulk perovskite crystals (17 nm). Therefore, impregnation over alumina
391 does not appear to induce important structural changes. However, a lesser degree of
392 perovskite loading leads to smaller crystals. For example, 30% LSCO/Al₂O₃ crystals
393 were 12 nm in diameter. A smaller crystal size is indicative of partial inhibition of
394 perovskite agglomeration during the calcination step [32]. This inhibition causes the
395 perovskite to be highly dispersed over the alumina support. The crystallinity of the
396 perovskite phase could not be determined in the case of loadings of less 20%. In these
397 cases, the perovskite diffraction peaks were weak or absent, a further indication of the
398 high degree of perovskite dispersion.

399 TEM images of the bulk perovskite and the 30% LSCO/Al₂O₃ catalyst were acquired
400 (Figure 4). In agreement with past reports [33], the bare perovskite (Figure 4a)
401 contained highly crystalline particles with visible crystal edges. The crystals were
402 heterogeneous in size and measured from 50 nm to 150 nm in diameter. On the other
403 hand, the alumina-supported perovskite (Figure 4b) had an alumina phase with small
404 crystals (light grey) and perovskite rich areas (dark grey). Impregnating alumina with
405 perovskite decreases the particle sizes (20-50 nm) [33]. This result is consistent with the
406 above XRD data.

407

FIGURE 4

408 Perovskite loading of the samples were verified by ICP-AES (Table 2). Meanwhile, the
409 relevant textural properties were determined by N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms
410 (Table 2). In all cases, the perovskite loading was found to be very close to the nominal

411 values. The specific surface areas (SSA) of bare alumina and bulk perovskite were 186
412 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$ and $20 \text{ m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$, respectively. The SSA of bulk perovskite was small, but it was
413 larger than the SSA had been reported in the past for similar formations [34-36]. The
414 SSA of alumina-supported samples correlates adequately with the weighted average of
415 bare alumina and perovskite SSA values. Thus the SSA increases according to the
416 degree of perovskite loading. The same trend is observed with pore volume.

417

TABLE 2

418 UV–Vis–NIR spectra of the alumina-supported-perovskites, bulk perovskite, and
419 alumina were acquired (Figure 5). The spectra of the 40% and 50% LSCO/ Al_2O_3
420 samples (>30% loading) are similar to the spectrum of the bulk LSCO. The bands
421 observed in the 230-380 nm range of the spectra correspond to signals from Co^{3+} ions
422 that have an octahedral coordination and to signals that are due to charge transfers from
423 oxygen to metal oxide in oxide structures. Both types of signals are characteristic of
424 bulk LaCoO_3 perovskites [37, 38]. Meanwhile, the UV–Vis–NIR spectra of the 10%
425 and 20% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 differ (<30% loading): each has a triplet with peaks located at
426 545, 580, 630 nm and another whose peaks are found at 1230, 1340 and 1530 nm.
427 These bands correspond to signals from Co^{2+} ions found in a tetrahedral arrangement in
428 the form of cobalt aluminate (CoAl_2O_4) [39, 40]. This formation is a consequence of the
429 migration of Co^{2+} ions into tetrahedral sites of an $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ lattice. The assignment of the
430 CoAl_2O_4 bands is corroborated by the UV–Vis–NIR spectra of a synthesized bulk
431 cobalt aluminate sample (Figure S4). The CoAl_2O_4 forms because low perovskite
432 loadings lead to more disperse perovskite particles. The perovskite-alumina interaction
433 is enhanced in the presence of low perovskite loadings. There are two additional
434 absorption bands at around 1930 and 2230 nm. These bands correspond to signals from
435 water molecules and surface hydroxyl groups, both of which are characteristic of
436 alumina supports [41].

437

FIGURE 5

438 Hydrogen consumption profiles of the samples were determined by temperature
439 programmed reduction experiments (H_2 -TPR). These profiles are shown in Figure 6.
440 Reducible species were not detected in the bare alumina in the range of temperatures
441 that was assessed. Therefore, the H_2 -TPR signal was normalized according perovskite
442 mass. Normalization allowed us to more accurately contrast the redox properties of the

443 samples. The consumption profile of the bulk $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ has two main regions: one
444 above 500 °C and one below. H_2 consumption below 500 °C is a consequence of the
445 reduction of oxygen that is chemisorbed on the catalyst surface and the progressive
446 reduction of Co^{3+} to Co^{2+} from the surface to the inner layers, maintaining the
447 perovskite structure [42-45],

449 Hydrogen consumption at higher temperatures is due to the reduction of Co^{2+} to Co^0 ,
450 also beginning from the surface and progressing to the bulk layer.

452 In agreement with UV–Vis–NIR spectra, LSCO/ Al_2O_3 samples with a perovskite
453 loading above 30% have a hydrogen consumption profile similar to the bulk perovskite.
454 Meanwhile, strong differences were observed with LSCO/ Al_2O_3 samples with loading
455 values below 30%. In fact, no reducible species were detected with the 10%
456 LSCO/ Al_2O_3 sample until a temperature of 800 °C was reached, highlighting the limited
457 reducibility of the cobalt species in the sample. High cobalt stability under reducing
458 environments is due to the formation of cobalt aluminate [46-48]. Indeed, synthesized
459 bulk cobalt aluminate has a similar H_2 consumption profile (Figure S5). In the case of
460 the 20% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 sample, the high temperature H_2 consumption due to the presence
461 of CoAl_2O_4 is still evident although with lower intensity than in the 10% LSCO/ Al_2O_3
462 sample. Furthermore, small H_2 consumption is observed for temperatures lower than
463 800 °C. This lower temperature consumption is indicative of the formation of a small
464 fraction of perovskite. In the case of 30% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 , the hydrogen consumption at
465 temperatures below 800 °C was notably higher. This result unequivocally reveals the
466 formation of perovskite and the inhibition of CoAl_2O_4 formation. In conclusion, a 30%
467 loading level is enough for a monolayer to form over the alumina. Monolayer formation
468 leads to the formation of the desired perovskite phase. Higher loading results in a higher
469 level of H_2 consumption, a consequence of cobalt ion reduction and less CoAl_2O_4
470 mediated hydrogen consumption. Hydrogen consumption at temperatures around
471 150 °C is mediated by oxygen vacancies [9]. Importantly, this type of consumption is
472 more prominent in the 30%, 40%, and 50% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 samples.

473 The H₂ consumption profiles were integrated in order to calculate H₂/Co ratios (Table
474 3). Bulk perovskite has a H₂/Co ratio of 1.49, which is very close to the theoretical
475 value of 1.5 (see Equations 8 and 9). This result is consistent with the model that all the
476 cobalt in the sample was in the form of Co³⁺ ions. Meanwhile, a theoretical H₂/Co value
477 of 1 is expected in the case of the complete reduction of CoAl₂O₄ to cobalt (CoAl₂O₄ +
478 H₂ → Co + Al₂O₃ + H₂O). Thus, the progressive decrease in the H₂/Co ratio from 1.27
479 (50% LSCO/Al₂O₃) to 0.86 (10% LSCO/Al₂O₃) supports the idea that CoAl₂O₄ forms at
480 the expense of the perovskite at reduced levels of loading. Importantly, the H₂/Co ratio
481 is below 1 for 10% LSCO/Al₂O₃ sample. This is because the reduction of Co²⁺ ions in
482 CoAl₂O₄ was incomplete at the maximum temperature tested (950 °C). The same results
483 were seen with the CoAl₂O₄ sample (Figure S5).

484

FIGURE 6

485

TABLE 3

486 *3.2.2. NO_x storage and reduction behaviour of alumina-supported perovskites.*
487 Conversion of NO-to-NO₂ ($X_{\text{NO-to-NO}_2}$) by the samples was measured at different
488 temperatures (Figure 7). As previously reported for bulk samples, NO conversion
489 initially increases with temperature, a consequence of enhanced oxidation kinetics. In
490 contrast, at temperatures above 350-400 °C, NO conversion decreases with temperature
491 in the same type of thermodynamic equilibrium-controlled regime that is seen in
492 exothermal reactions [11, 12, 24]. The more highly loaded the sample, the more
493 efficiently it oxidizes NO in the kinetically controlled regime (T<400 °C). In fact, the
494 50% LSCO/Al₂O₃ sample has the best NO-to-NO₂ conversion outcomes. The maximum
495 conversion with this sample is 72.4% at 350 °C (Table 4). This result is expected
496 because perovskite is the active component that mediates the oxidation reactions (Figure
497 S7). However, the 50% LSCO/Al₂O₃ was significantly better at oxidizing NO than the
498 LSCO alone. NO oxidation per unit of perovskite mass increased when the perovskite is
499 impregnated onto the alumina. Therefore, depositing the perovskite onto alumina makes
500 more efficient use of the perovskite.

501

FIGURE 7

502 Specific NO oxidation rates were calculated for the supported samples at 350 °C using
503 Equation 2 (Table 4). The specific NO oxidation rates were also calculated for Al₂O₃,

504 CoAl₂O₄ and LSCO samples as are seen in Figure 7. The specific NO oxidation rate *per*
505 *gram of bare alumina* was almost negligible (1.4 μmol min⁻¹ (g cat.)⁻¹) and a low value
506 was also calculated for cobalt aluminate (14.6 μmol min⁻¹ (g cat.)⁻¹). These observations
507 are consistent with the results shown in Figure S7.

508 However, when considering the mass of perovskite found in each sample, the results are
509 more dramatic. All alumina-supported samples had higher specific NO oxidation rate
510 *per gram of perovskite* than LSCO alone, which had a rate 48.6 μmol min⁻¹ (g LSCO)⁻¹.
511 In the case of 20% LSCO/Al₂O₃ sample, the formation of CoAl₂O₄ was still evident.
512 However, the formation of a rather small fraction of perovskite is enough to notably
513 enhance oxidation capacity. For the 20% sample, the specific NO oxidation rate *per*
514 *gram of perovskite* is 131.7 μmol min⁻¹ (g LSCO)⁻¹, nearly triple the rate of the bulk
515 LSCO. The specific NO reaction rate *per gram of perovskite* is higher for the 30%
516 sample, reaching 138.1 μmol min⁻¹ (g LSCO)⁻¹. At 30%, the perovskite phase continues
517 to develop and the amount of CoAl₂O₄ becomes almost negligible. The specific NO
518 reaction rate *per gram of perovskite* decreases for the supported samples with perovskite
519 loadings of 40% and 50%. This happens because the perovskite begins to agglomerate
520 on the support at these percentages. Thus, the 30% sample has the maximum specific
521 NO oxidation rate *per gram of perovskite*. High oxidation rates can be explained in the
522 following way: accessibility to the oxidation sites is enhanced because of how well-
523 developed and well-distributed the perovskite phase is over the alumina.

524 **TABLE 4**

525 NO_x storage capacity (*NSC*), global NO_x conversion (*X*_{NO_x}) and nitrogen production (
526 *Y*_{N₂}) were determined for the alumina-supported samples (Figure 8). These values were
527 calculated using the information from prior NO_x storage and reduction experiments
528 (Figure S6).

529 There is a progressive increase of NO_x storage capacity (*NSC*) up to a temperature of
530 400-450 °C (Figure 8a). NO₂ formation is limited at higher temperatures, however. This
531 is due to a switch to a thermodynamically controlled regime and a decrease in the
532 stability of stored nitrates. This is why *NSC* decreases at higher temperatures. Higher
533 perovskite loading results in a higher *NSC* at every temperature assayed. This is because
534 the higher loading results in a better balance between NO₂ concentration sites and NO_x

535 adsorption sites. As previously discussed, NO-to-NO₂ oxidation is limited when the
536 loading is below 30% because CoAl₂O₄ preferentially forms. Samples with less than
537 30% loading do not have an impressive oxidation capacity and low perovskite loading
538 results in NO_x storage site defects. However, in contrast with the results of the NO-to-
539 NO₂ conversion values, the *NSC* of the 50% LSCO/Al₂O₃ sample is similar to the *NSC*
540 of the 40% LSCO/Al₂O₃ sample. It appears that decreasing LSCO dispersion limits NO_x
541 adsorption site accessibility.

542

FIGURE 8

543 The *NSC* calculated for the samples at 400 °C were normalized according to the mass of
544 perovskite in the samples (Table 4). Consistent with the specific NO conversion rates
545 *per gram of perovskite*, 30% LSCO/Al₂O₃ has an *NSC* three times higher than bulk
546 perovskite. This is because the 30% sample has a higher NO oxidation capacity and
547 higher trapping site accessibility. Under these conditions, the diffusion of intermediate
548 compounds from oxidation to the adsorption sites is favored.

549 The amount of NO_x converted was assessed with respect to the amount of NO fed into
550 the system (X_{NO_x}) at different temperatures (Figure 8b). Here, X_{NO_x} increases with
551 perovskite loading. However, in contrast to the *NSC*, this improvement is only observed
552 up to the 30% sample. As with bulk perovskites, it appears that NO_x reduction is the
553 rate limiting step in the conversion process. Although *NSC* is further enhanced at higher
554 perovskite loadings, the same is not true for X_{NO_x} values.

555 However, X_{NO_x} is clearly higher in the supported samples than in the bulk LSCO. The
556 maximum X_{NO_x} for the supported samples is 48.8% for the 40% LSCO/Al₂O₃ variant.
557 The X_{NO_x} of the bulk LSCO is as low as 13.3%. Thus, perovskite impregnation onto
558 alumina also promotes the NO_x reduction activity of the perovskite. This conclusion is
559 also supported by data showing higher NH₃ and N₂O concentrations at the reactor outlet
560 with supported samples than with unsupported samples (Figure S6).

561 Nitrogen yields are also higher in alumina-supported samples (Figure 8c) than in the
562 bulk samples, however the difference is more modest than with the NO_x storage
563 capacity and global NO_x conversion values. The maximum N₂ yield at 450 °C is 8% and
564 17% for bulk LSCO and 40% LSCO/Al₂O₃, respectively. The reason why N₂ yield is
565 not enhanced more is that that NO_x adsorption site regeneration is limited in the absence

566 of precious metals. In addition, NH_3 formation is favored at high temperatures. In fact,
567 NH_3 yields are 27% for the 40% sample and as low as 7% for the bulk LSCO (Figure
568 9b).

569 **FIGURE 9**

570 *3.3. Pd-based alumina-supported perovskites vs. bulk perovskite for NO_x storage and*
571 *reduction.* Due to the promising results observed for alumina-supported perovskite
572 based catalysts, we decided to also study the effects of adding 1.5 wt% palladium (Pd)
573 to the 30% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 and bulk LSCO.

574 The NO-to- NO_2 conversion ($X_{\text{NO-to-NO}_2}$), NO_x storage capacity (NSC), global NO_x
575 conversion (X_{NO_x}) and nitrogen production (Y_{N_2}) values for the Pd impregnated samples
576 were calculated at various temperatures (Figure 10). The Pt-based model NSR catalyst
577 was used as the reference sample. Adding Pd did not improve maximum NO-to- NO_2
578 conversion value (Figure 10a). This confirms that the perovskite functions as the
579 primary NO oxidation catalyst and that the contribution of the Pd is minimal.
580 Perovskite-based more efficiently promotes NO oxidation (above 60%) than the
581 reference Pt-Ba/ Al_2O_3 catalyst. The Pt-Ba/ Al_2O_3 sample has a conversion rating of 40%.

582 In contrast to the observed NO conversion values, NO_x storage capacity improves
583 significantly upon palladium incorporation (Figure 10b). The Pd-30% LSCO/ Al_2O_3
584 catalyst has the highest NSC : about 80% at 350 °C. This is higher than the NSC of the
585 Pd/LSCO which hovers at 70%. The higher NSC can be attributed to close contacts
586 between the well-dispersed perovskite particles and the palladium particles. These
587 contacts are facilitated by the higher surface area provided by the alumina support. NO_x
588 reduction is the rate limiting step of the process in the absence of Pd. The incorporation
589 of palladium and the close contacts this metal makes with the perovskite improves the
590 NO_x reduction rate. Thus, NO_x storage and reduction is improved by incorporating Pd.

591 In addition, promoting the storage of NO_x via the nitrate route, a consequence of a
592 higher NO-to- NO_2 conversion rate for Pd-30% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 [49-51], results in a higher
593 NSC than with the model Pt-Ba/ Al_2O_3 catalyst (70% at 400 °C).

594 Pd incorporation significantly improves the global NO_x conversion value and N_2 yield
595 (Figure 10c and 10d), particularly at lower temperatures. Pd-30% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 has the

596 highest global NO_x conversion value ($X_{\text{NO}_x}=75\%$) at 350 °C, (Figure 10c). This
597 formulation also has the highest N₂ yield ($Y_{\text{N}_2}=65\%$ at 350 °C, Figure 10d).

598

FIGURE 10

599 4. CONCLUSIONS

600 Partially substituting the lanthanum by Sr enhances the NO_x storage and reduction
601 capacity of the La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO₃ perovskites. In particular, this method improves the NO_x
602 storage capacity (*NSC*) of the perovskite samples. Among the strontium doped samples,
603 La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ has the highest *NSC* (55.8%) at 400 °C, which is significantly better than
604 the *NSC* of bare LaCoO₃ (33.6%).

605 Different loadings of La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ perovskite were used to impregnate alumina as
606 support (LSCO/Al₂O₃). Interestingly, UV–Vis–NIR and H₂-TPR experiments reveal
607 that, in the case of low perovskite loading (<10%), cobalt ions are exclusively
608 coordinated in a tetrahedral arrangement, in the form of cobalt aluminate (CoAl₂O₄).
609 Meanwhile a well-developed and predominant perovskite phase was detected with
610 perovskite loadings above 30%.

611 In addition, the 30% LSCO/Al₂O₃ has highest specific NO oxidation rate *per gram of*
612 *perovskite* at 350 °C (138.1 μmol min⁻¹ (g LSCO)⁻¹). This is more than twice what was
613 observed with bulk perovskite, which has an oxidation rate of only 48.6 μmol min⁻¹
614 (g LSCO)⁻¹. This improvement is due to having a perovskite phase that is well
615 distributed over the Al₂O₃, which enhances accessibility to oxidation sites.

616 The 30% LSCO/Al₂O₃ formulation also has the highest NO_x adsorption capacity *per*
617 *gram of perovskite*: around 306 μmol (g LSCO)⁻¹ at 400 °C. This is a significant
618 improvement over un-supported perovskite, which has a capacity of 115 μmol
619 (g LSCO)⁻¹. This enhancement is due to a higher NO oxidation capacity and higher
620 trapping site accessibility, which in turn, facilitates the diffusion of intermediate
621 compounds from oxidation sites to adsorption sites.

622 The global NO_x conversion value goes up from 13.3% at 450 °C for the un-supported
623 sample to 48.8% for the 40% LSCO/Al₂O₃ alumina-supported catalyst. Finally, the

624 nitrogen yield improves to a lesser extent because the alumina-supported samples
625 promote NH_3 formation at the expense of nitrogen production. Nevertheless, the
626 nitrogen yield of the 40% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 sample is around 17%, approximately double
627 what was observed for the reference bulk sample.

628 Incorporating $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ perovskite onto alumina inhibits the crystal growth of bulk
629 perovskites, one of the primary limitations of this material. Among the prepared
630 catalysts, the 30% $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ sample makes the most efficient use of the
631 perovskite phase, which suggests that it is a promising base catalyst for use in
632 automobile applications.

633 However, the NO_x reduction capacity of the alumina-supported material is still limited
634 at low temperatures. In a preliminary effort to improve the catalytic behaviour of the
635 alumina-supported material, we show that incorporating a small amount of palladium
636 can have a positive effect under rich and low temperature conditions.

637 Incorporating palladium improves the NO_x removal efficiency of alumina-supported
638 perovskites. This is due to closer contacts between the NO_x reducing sites and NO
639 oxidation and adsorption sites, i.e. palladium and perovskite phases, respectively. A
640 material consisting of 1.5% Pd-30% $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ achieves a comparable or
641 even superior catalytic performance than the model Pt-based catalyst.

642 Further studies have to be carried out to evaluate the real-world applicability of these
643 novel formulations. For example, it will be necessary to analyze the effects of H_2O and
644 CO_2 on the activity and durability of the materials developed here.

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650

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811 **TABLES AND FIGURES CAPTIONS**

812 **Table 1.** NO_x storage capacity (*NSC*), NO_x global conversion (X_{NO_x}) and nitrogen
813 production (Y_{N_2}) of samples with different Sr contents at 400 °C.

814 **Table 2.** Textural properties of alumina support (γ -Al₂O₃), La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃
815 perovskite (LSCO), and different loadings of LSCO onto alumina (y%
816 LSCO/Al₂O₃).

817 **Table 3.** Deconvoluted hydrogen consumption related to different reduction steps
818 for different weight loads of La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ perovskite supported over
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820 **Table 4.** NO-to-NO₂ conversions, the corresponding average specific reaction rates
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822 La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ bulk perovskite (LSCO) and different weight loads of this
823 formulation supported over γ -alumina (y% LSCO/Al₂O₃).

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825

826 **Figure 1.** NO, NO₂, NO_x (NO + NO₂), NH₃ and N₂O outlet concentration during two
827 consecutive lean-rich cycles in stationary state of: a) LaCoO₃ and b)
828 La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ perovskites at 400 °C.

829 **Figure 2.** Evolution with temperature of: a) NO_x storage capacity (*NSC*), b) NO_x
830 global conversion (X_{NO_x}) and c) N₂ production (Y_{N_2}) of La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO₃
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833 increasing La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ perovskite (LSCO) contents (\blacktriangle Al₂O₃ and \circ
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836 impregnated over alumina.

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838 perovskite (LSCO) and different weight loads of this formulation
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840 **Figure 6.** H_2 -TPR profiles of $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ samples with different perovskite
841 loads (y% LSCO/ Al_2O_3), as well as the bare perovskite counterpart
842 (LSCO), normalized according to grams of perovskite.

843 **Figure 7.** NO-to- NO_2 oxidation capacity of different $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ perovskite loads
844 supported by alumina (10, 20, 30, 40 or 50 wt% LSCO/ Al_2O_3) and bulk
845 $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ perovskite, as reference.

846 **Figure 8.** Changes in: a) NO_x storage capacity (NSC), b) NO_x global conversion
847 (X_{NO_x}) and c) nitrogen production (Y_{N_2}) at a range of temperatures of
848 $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ perovskite supported by alumina (y% LSCO/ Al_2O_3), along
849 with reference bulk sample (LSCO).

850 **Figure 9.** Changes at a range of temperatures of: a) ammonia production (Y_{NH_3}) and
851 b) nitrous oxide ($Y_{\text{N}_2\text{O}}$) for increasing perovskite loads supported over
852 alumina (y% LSCO/ Al_2O_3), along with reference bulk sample (LSCO).

853 **Figure 10.** Changes in: a) NO-to- NO_2 conversion, b) NO_x storage capacity (NSC), c)
854 NO_x global conversion (X_{NO_x}) and c) nitrogen production (Y_{N_2}) with
855 temperature for 1,5% Pd-30% LSCO/ Al_2O_3 , 1,5% Pd/LSCO and NSR
856 model catalyst (1.5% Pt-15% $\text{BaO}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$).

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Table 1.

860

NO_x storage capacity (*NSC*), NO_x global conversion (*X*_{NO_x}) and nitrogen production

861

(*Y*_{N₂}) of samples with different Sr contents at 400 °C.

Sample	<i>NSC</i> , μmol (g LSCO) ⁻¹	<i>X</i> _{NO_x} , μmol (g LSCO) ⁻¹	<i>Y</i> _{N₂} , μmol (g LSCO) ⁻¹
LaCoO ₃	34.8 (33.6%)	12.3 (10.5%)	2.3 (3.9%)
La _{0.9} Sr _{0.1} CoO ₃	40.6 (39.2%)	12.6 (10.7%)	2.3 (4.0%)
La _{0.8} Sr _{0.2} CoO ₃	53.0 (51.2%)	16.7 (14.2%)	3.9 (6.7%)
La _{0.7} Sr _{0.3} CoO ₃	57.8 (55.8%)	17.0 (14.5%)	4.0 (6.9%)
La _{0.6} Sr _{0.4} CoO ₃	56.1 (54.2%)	14.6 (12.4%)	3.5 (6.0%)
La _{0.5} Sr _{0.5} CoO ₃	52.6 (50.8%)	15.1 (12.9%)	3.9 (6.8%)

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Table 2.

865 Textural properties of alumina support (γ -Al₂O₃), La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ perovskite (LSCO), and different
 866 loadings of LSCO onto alumina (y% LSCO/Al₂O₃).

Sample	Perovskite loading, %	Surface area, m ² g ⁻¹	V _p , cm ³ g ⁻¹	d _c , nm
γ -Al ₂ O ₃	-	186	0.63	-
10% LSCO/Al ₂ O ₃	11	147	0.44	-
20% LSCO/Al ₂ O ₃	20	124	0.32	-
30% LSCO/Al ₂ O ₃	29	119	0.36	12
40% LSCO/Al ₂ O ₃	39	98	0.29	15
50% LSCO/Al ₂ O ₃	53	83	0.24	17
LSCO	100	20	0.12	17

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Table 3.

870 Deconvoluted hydrogen consumption related to different reduction steps for different weight loads of
871 $\text{La}_{0.7}\text{Sr}_{0.3}\text{CoO}_3$ perovskite supported over alumina ($y\%$ LSCO/ Al_2O_3), along with reference bulk
872 sample.

Sample	H_2/Co
10% LSCO/ Al_2O_3	0.86
20% LSCO/ Al_2O_3	0.98
30% LSCO/ Al_2O_3	1.12
40% LSCO/ Al_2O_3	1.26
50% LSCO/ Al_2O_3	1.27
LSCO	1.49

873

874

Table 4.

875 NO-to-NO₂ conversions, the corresponding average specific reaction rates (\bar{R}_{NO}) at 350 °C, and NO_x
 876 storage capacities (*NSC*) at 400 °C of La_{0.7}Sr_{0.3}CoO₃ bulk perovskite (LSCO) and different weight
 877 loads of this formulation supported over γ -alumina (*y*% LSCO/Al₂O₃).

Sample	$X_{NO-to-NO_2}$, %	\bar{R}_{NO}^a , $\mu\text{mol min}^{-1} (\text{g cat.})^{-1}$	\bar{R}_{NO}^b , $\mu\text{mol min}^{-1} (\text{g LSCO})^{-1}$	<i>NSC</i> ^a , $\mu\text{mol (g cat.)}^{-1}$	<i>NSC</i> ^b , $\mu\text{mol (g LSCO)}^{-1}$
γ -Al ₂ O ₃	1.8	1.4	--	3.2	--
CoAl ₂ O ₄	17.4	14.6	--	50.4	--
10% LSCO/Al ₂ O ₃	11.2	9.4	81.3	29.8	226.5
20% LSCO/Al ₂ O ₃	32.9	27.5	131.7	65.2	294.2
30% LSCO/Al ₂ O ₃	51.1	42.4	138.1	97.3	305.8
40% LSCO/Al ₂ O ₃	65.4	54.3	133.7	123.6	297.1
50% LSCO/Al ₂ O ₃	72.4	60.2	118.9	103.2	198.1
LSCO	61.1	48.6	48.6	115.0	115.0

878 ^a Normalized per sample mass (g cat.⁻¹).

879 ^b Normalized per perovskite mass ((g LSCO)⁻¹).

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